

Metabolic Processes In Plants Under The Influence Of High Temperature

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Abstract: Resistance to high temperature in many cases depends on the period of its exposure, its absolute value. Most of the agricultural crops begin to suffer when the ambient air temperature reaches 35-40 °C. At this and higher temperatures, a number of physiological processes taking place in the plant cease, and when it approaches 50 °C, the cell cytoplasm condenses and its destruction occurs.

Keywords — plants, temperature, factors, metabolism, negative effect, positive effect, atmospheric air, pressure.

INTRODUCTION.

An increase in temperature that is optimal for the plant leads to partial or mass denaturation of proteins in the cell. This has a negative effect on the disruption of the protein-lipid complex of the plasmollem and the functioning of other membranes in the cell. Provard results in violation of the osmotic properties of the cell. Many tasks performed by the cell are lost, the speed of various physiological processes slows down. For example, at a temperature of 20 °C, mitosis occurs at the rate of division in all cells of a plant, when the air temperature rises to 38 °C, mitosis occurs in one out of seven cells, and when the temperature rises to 42 °C, the dividing 513 only one of the cells divides.

The effect of high temperature on the protein-lipid complex in cells and tissues can be seen as follows: at a temperature of 22 °C, nuclear disintegration does not occur at all. At 38 °C, 5.3% of the studied cells were destroyed, and at 50 °C, practically all nuclei were destroyed. When the maximum temperature for a plant occurs, the decomposition and consumption of organic substances in the process of respiration is greater than their formation. As carbohydrates decrease in the plant, it begins to open. This situation is clearly manifested in wheat, potatoes and other homestead crops grown in temperate climates. "Draining" the plant from the ground makes it more susceptible to fungal diseases.

The high temperature affecting the plant has a stronger negative effect on photosynthesis than on the respiration processes taking place in it. A number of reactions that carry out photosynthesis are somewhat more sensitive to high air temperatures than those in respiratory processes. Below the optimal temperature, plant growth and the process of photosynthesis almost stop photoassimilation. This process is associated with changes in the activity of enzymes. At this time, the exchange of gases in the respiratory process increases, its energy efficiency decreases, poisoning of the protoplasm occurs under the influence of decomposition products (ammonia). All these processes cause the plant to

"exhaust" and stress it. Symptoms of "burn" are formed in some places of the leaf. In plants that are genetically adapted to the effects of high temperatures, compounds are formed that bind substances such as excess ammonia, which causes poisoning in such cases.

Proteins that can withstand stress are synthesized in the cells of plants directly affected by high temperature. Plants in open areas are much more resistant to the effects of high temperatures than those in the shade. A very high (43-45 °C) temperature, even if it affects it for a short time, has a destructive effect on the plant and causes it to dry up. Prevention of overheating of the plant is provided by watering it with water, the water from the root increases the process of transpiration through the leaves. As a result, water exchange in the plant increases and it cools down.

As a result of the transpiration that occurs in the plant through the leaves, the temperature sometimes drops to 10-15 °C. Plants with closed leaf tips and fast wilting plants dry out faster than those with sufficient water supply. The plant tolerates dry hot weather more easily than humid heat. When the air humidity is high and the temperature is high, the control of leaf temperature by transpiration is limited.

An increase in air temperature is especially dangerous for a plant when its illumination is strong. In order to reduce the level of exposure to the sun's rays, plant leaves are placed with the edge facing the light. Such a position is called an erectoid position. When the sunlight strongly affects the leaf, the movement of chloroplasts in the cell accelerates, thus it goes into a hole that protects itself. The plant is protected from the strong influence of sunlight by forming the following morphological and physiological changes:

1. The color of the body gives the color of discharge.
2. Twists and closes the leaves.
3. In order to protect internal tissues from overheating, they form soft hairs or scales on the surface of the leaf.

4. To protect the phloem and cambium, the phloem layer is thinned.

5. The cuticle thickens on the bark of the stem.

6. Carbohydrates increase in the cell cytoplasm and decrease the amount of water.

When the plant is dehydrated and thirsty in field conditions, high temperature has a fatal effect on it. When the leaves of a plant or its whole body wither a lot, a number of other physiological processes are disturbed, in addition to profound changes in the processes of photosynthesis and respiration. The resistance of the plant to the high temperature of atmospheric air depends on its ontogeny - the periods of growth and development. The greatest destructive effect of high temperature corresponds to the initial periods of growth and development. Actively developing young tissues are less resistant to high temperatures than old, old, "resting" ones. Different parts of the plant have different resistance to high temperature: the underground part is less resistant, the stem, branch, buds are somewhat more resistant.

He quickly begins to adapt to heat stress that occurs in plants. The plant starts preparing for the effect of high temperature several hours earlier. When the days are hot, the resistance of plants to its high temperature is stronger after choshgoh, and weaker before choshgoh. Usually, this resistance is not stable, it does not get stronger, it disappears when the air temperature drops.

During the formation of generative organs in plants, resistance to high temperature decreases in annual and biennial plants.

The harmful effect of high temperature is especially strong on plants growing in dry conditions. For example, the formation of spikes begins during the period of wheat. A high temperature in the soil and atmospheric air causes damage to the growth cone, as a result of which the number of spikes, the amount of flowers in it decreases, and the yield in the provard is significantly reduced. The occurrence of drought in the soil due to the decrease of moisture in it, the high temperature of the air during the formation of spikes in grain plants causes damage to the flower buds in it, and the end of spike formation, it causes it to dry up. As a result, the number of ears without grain increases. For most of the plants, the high temperature of the atmosphere is dangerous, especially during their flowering period, it causes the flower to drop, the node does not develop, and it causes sterility. To determine the resistance of plants to high temperature, the studied plant leaf is placed in a chamber with high humidity and temperature for a certain period of time. The resistance is determined according to the signs of wounds formed on the leaves, branches and other places of the plant. According to F. F. Moskov method, the studied plant is taken from the leaf and placed in water with a temperature of 40, 45, 50 to 80 °C for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, remove the leaf and put it in cold water for 10 minutes. After that, 0.2 normal is transferred to HC1 solution. Infected and dried areas of the leaf turn brown. The number of them is determined by

determining the surface and how much they can withstand. In addition, resistance to high temperatures can be determined by the conductivity of protoplasm. A decrease in conductivity determines the inability to with stand high temperatures.

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